

THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE OF MULTIGRAVIDA MOTHERS ABOUT POST PLASENTA INTRA UTERI DEVICE (IUD) CONTRACEPTIVE METHODS AT PUSKESMAS PAHANDUT

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Abstract

Background : IUD is the suitable contraception promoted by health workers (midwives) for multigravida women, as it aligns with the number of children and the mother's age for spacing pregnancies. The aim of this research is to determine the level of knowledge of multigravida mothers about the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD). *Method* : This research is a descriptive research. The population of multigravida mothers at the Puskesmas Pahandut is 41 and the sample taken consists to 41 respondents. By using total sampling techniques, data collection is conducted using a questionnaire. The data analyzed by editing, coding, scoring and tabulating, also presented it in the form of tables. *Result* : The results of the research about the knowledge of multigravida mothers regarding the post-placenta Intrauterine Device (IUD) from 41 respondents are 12 (29%) respondents having low knowledge, 17 (42%) respondents having sufficient knowledge, and 12 (29%) respondents having good knowledge. *Conclusion* : The level of knowledge of multigravida mothers about the Post-Placenta Intrauterine Device (IUD) is mostly sufficient. It is hoped that healthcare providers enhance the information about the Post-Placenta Intrauterine Device (IUD) and promote it using media, so the information can be easily understood by multigravida mothers.

Keywords : Post Placenta, IUD, Multigravida

1. INTRODUCTION

Multigravida is a mother who has been pregnant more than once, up to three times. For women who are pregnant two times or more (multigravida), the suitable contraception promoted by health workers (midwives) is the IUD, as it aligns with the number of children and the mother's age for spacing pregnancies. The intrauterine device (IUD) is a flexible plastic contraceptive device that is placed in the uterus. The post-placental intrauterine device (IUD) is a type of intrauterine contraceptive that is inserted within 10 minutes after the placenta is delivered during vaginal childbirth. The intrauterine device (IUD) as a post-placental contraceptive method has an effectiveness about 99.4%, which can prevent pregnancy for 5-10 years. Inserting it 10 minutes after the placenta is delivered will not cause significant pain, unlike the insertion of an IUD during the menstrual cycle [2]. However, in reality most multigravida mothers prefer to use injectable contraceptives or hormonal pills, and very few of them choose post-placental IUDs, because information about injectable contraceptives and

pills is more frequently obtained and known by multigravida mothers. Meanwhile, the post-placental intrauterine device (IUD) is chosen less frequently by multigravida mothers due to the insufficient information that provided by health workers, as well as it's being influenced by education levels and culture of multigravida mothers.

According to the Indonesian Health Profile in 2016, the number of childbearing age couples (CBA) was 48,536,690, with new family planning participants that using the intrauterine device (IUD) about 481,564 (7.23%). In Central Borneo Province, the number of childbearing age couples was 1,416,867, with new family planning participants using the intrauterine device (IUD) about 1,043 (0.53%). According to the Profile of the Dinas Kesehatan Kota Palangka Raya in 2016, the number of childbearing age couples was 40,164, and the number of new family planning participants using the intrauterine device (IUD) method was 37 (3.9%). From the data of Puskesmas Pahandut, the number of participants using the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD) is 0 (0.0%), while from the data of the delivery room at Dr. Doris Sylvanus in 2017, there were 2,864 mothers giving birth, with participants using the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD) also totaling 0 (0.0%), and participants using the intrauterine device (IUD) during cesarean section (C-section) amounting to 5 (0.17%). Based on that data, it can be seen that the acceptance of IUD contraceptives is still low at the national, provincial, city and even at hospitals and community health centers.

Contraception that can be used by postpartum and has the highest potential to prevent missed opportunities for family planning is the post-placental intrauterine device (IUD) [3]. Most mothers refuse to have the post-placental IUD inserted due to concerns and fear of complications [4]. A woman's fertility can return within a few weeks after childbirth, which can create the opportunity for an unwanted pregnancy. If a multigravida mother does not immediately use contraception after childbirth, she risks unwanted pregnancy, which will increase the incidence of abortion. Moreover, an inappropriate interval between births has been proven to have negative effects on women's health and socio-economic well-being.

Efforts that can be made for multigravida mothers include providing communication, information, and education (KIE), promoting and introducing the post-placental Intrauterine Device (IUD) as a contraceptive method. Based on that description, the researcher is interested in studying "The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers about the Post Placenta Intrauterine Device (IUD) at Puskesmas Pahandut".

2. METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this study is descriptive research, which is a method conducted with the primary aim of creating a depiction or description of a particular state or area of a specific population that is factual, objective, systematic, and accurate. The purpose of this research is to determine the level of knowledge of multigravida mothers about the Post Placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

3. RESULTS

The results of data collection conducted at the Puskesmas Pahandut regarding the level of knowledge of multigravida mothers about the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD), with total of 41 respondents are presented to two types: general data and specific data. The general data, which represents the characteristics of the research subjects, includes education, occupation, age, number of pregnancies, whether they have received information about the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD), and the sources of that information. Meanwhile, the

specific data pertains to the level of knowledge of multigravida mothers about the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

3.1 General Data

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Based on Education

Characteristics	N	%
Elementary school	10	24
Junior high school	21	51
High school	8	20
Collage	2	5

Out of 41 respondents, 10 (24%) mothers have an elementary school education, 21 (51%) have a junior high school education, 8 (20%) have a senior high school education, and 2 (5%) have a college education.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents Based on Occupation

Characteristics	N	%
Civil servants	0	0
Military/police	0	0
Private sector	10	24
Housewives	31	76

Out of 41 respondents, there were 0 (0%) civil servants, 0 (0%) members of the military/police, 10 (24%) from the private sector, and 31 (76%) housewives.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents Based on Age

Characteristics	N	%
<20 years old	0	0
20-35 years old	37	90
35-44 years old	4	10

Out of 41 respondents, the number of mothers under 20 years old is 0 (0%), aged 20-35 years is 37 (90%), and aged 35-45 years is 4 (10%).

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents Based on The Number Of Pregnancies

Characteristics	N	%
Second pregnancy	20	49
Third pregnancy	11	27
Fourth or more pregnancy	10	24

Out of 41 respondents, 20 (49%) are pregnant with their second child, 11 (27%) are pregnant with their third child, and 10 (24%) are pregnant with four or more children.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents Based on Having Received The Information Before

Characteristics	N	%
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Ever received	20	49
Never received	21	51

Out of 41 respondents who received information about the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD), 20 (49%) had received information, while 21 (51%) had never received information about it.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents Based on The Resource of Information

Characteristics	N	%
Healthcare workers	15	75
Electronic media	0	0
Print media	0	0
Family	0	0

Out of 20 respondents, 15 (75%) received information from healthcare workers (Midwives, Nurses, Doctors), 0 (0%) received information from Electronic Media (TV, Radio, Internet), 5 (25%) received information from Print Media (Newspapers, Magazines), and 0 (0%) received information from Family.

3.2 Specific Data

Table 7: The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers About the Post-Placental IUD

Characteristics	N	%
Good	10	24
Sufficient	14	34
Low	17	42

Out of 41 respondents, there were 17 (42%) respondents with low knowledge, 14 (34%) respondents with sufficient knowledge, and 10 (24%) respondents who had good knowledge about the definition of the intrauterine device (IUD) post-placenta.

Table 8: The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers About the Benefits of Post-Placental IUD

Characteristics	N	%
Good	8	20
Sufficient	19	46
Low	14	34

Out of 41 respondents, there were 14 (34%) respondents with low knowledge, 19 (46%) respondents with sufficient knowledge, and 8 (20%) respondents with good knowledge about the benefits of the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

Table 9: The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers About the Weaknesses of Post-Placental IUD

Characteristics	N	%
Good	8	20
Sufficient	22	54

Low	10	24
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Out of 41 respondents, there were 10 (24%) respondents with low knowledge, 22 (54%) respondents with sufficient knowledge, and 9 (22%) respondents with good knowledge about the weaknesses of the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

Table 10: *The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers About the Indications of Post-Placental IUD*

Characteristics	N	%
Good	9	22
Sufficient	18	44
Low	14	34

Out of 41 respondents, there were 14 (34%) respondents with low knowledge, 18 (44%), and 9 (22%) respondents had good knowledge about the indications for the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

Table 11: *The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers About the Contra-Indications of Post-Placental IUD*

Characteristics	N	%
Good	12	29
Sufficient	20	49
Low	9	22

Out of 41 respondents, there were 9 (22%) respondents with low knowledge, 20 (49%), and 12 (29%) respondents had good knowledge about the contraindications of the post placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

Table 12: *The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers About the Side Effects of Post-Placental IUD*

Characteristics	N	%
Good	5	12
Sufficient	24	59
Low	12	29

Out of 41 respondents, there were 12 (29%) respondents with low knowledge, 24 (59%) respondents with sufficient knowledge, and 5 (12%) respondents who had good knowledge about the side effects of the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

Table 13: *The Level of Knowledge of Multigravida Mothers About the Post-Placental IUD*

Characteristics	N	%
Good	12	29
Sufficient	17	42
Low	12	29

Out of 41 respondents, there were 12 (29%) respondents with low knowledge, 17 (42%) respondents with sufficient knowledge, and 12 (29%) respondents with good knowledge about the post-placenta intrauterine device (IUD).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The level of knowledge of multigravida mothers about the post-placental intrauterine device (IUD) is influenced by several factors, including education, occupation, age, number of pregnancies, whether they have received information before, and the sources of that information. These factors interact with each other, affecting multigravida mothers' knowledge and comprehension of the post-placental intrauterine device (IUD).

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